

ANALYSES OF THE TECHNIQUES FOR TEACHING COMPOSITION IN ENGLISH AT THE UPPER BASIC LEVEL IN ILORIN, NIGERIA.

By

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Abstract

The study analyzed the techniques for teaching composition in English language reflecting a sketch of the core academic system of the upper basic levels in Ilorin, Nigeria. It described the various techniques and the small number of principles of expository writing: The Status of English in Nigeria, The Place of Composition in the Upper Basic School Curriculum and Strategies for Effective Teaching and Learning of Composition. It also sketched the seriousness of the problems encountered by the teachers of English composition, suggesting remedies to the lapses that may be observed. Detailing the list of findings and the conclusions of the study, it presented suggestions for further researches.

Keywords : *Upper Basic School, Teaching Techniques*

Introduction

The ability to use language effectively is appropriately described as an art, and writing skills are a long-life necessity. As a painter uses colors and shapes, a writer uses words and structures to create images for the reader. Through language, people share stories, traditions, and values; they inform, describe, explain, and modify the behaviour of others, "Writing has come to occupy the prominent role it deserves in foreign language teaching and learning".

It is the teachers' task to help learners use the language effectively and appreciate the written expression of others. As it is well known, communication is the fundamental reason for the existence of language, and writing is a means towards it (Dunia, 2006). Moreover, students can compose and express themselves in written English, no matter what their level is; thus, *being able to write is a vital skill for speakers of a foreign language as much as for everyone using their own first language - (Harmer 2004:3).

The deficiency of any teacher in written as well as other aspects of English would no doubt affect the success of the objective of classroom interaction. This may be accountable for the recent poor performance of the Universal Basic Education and Post Basic Education students in public examinations in Nigeria. Hence, in a democratized nation like Nigeria, there is urgent need for improving students' performance in all aspects of English language, especially the written English (Harmer, 2004).

Statement of the Problem

Many researchers and scholars like Adegbite (2008), Olajide (2009) have written extensively on the poor performance of students in English Language. Many researchers, according to Babatunde (2003), he blamed the low English competence of students on poor attitude of teachers, the overall failure of the educational system, unavailability of instructional materials, poor policy implementation, inadequacies in the English language curriculum and confusion on what learners should be exposed to.

There have been studies on the challenges of improving students' performance in written English. However, none of these studies focused on the techniques used in teaching composition in English language at the upper basic level in Ilorin, Nigeria. Thus, this study intends to focus on secondary school teachers, with a view to identifying the various teaching techniques of English composition. By identifying such techniques, teachers may be helped

to overcome their teaching composition difficulties, at this education level.

Purpose of the Study

The primary purpose of this study is to analyze the techniques for teaching composition in English at the upper basic level in Ilorin, Nigeria

In specific terms, the study:

1. Identify the various techniques in the teaching of composition at the upper basic level in Ilorin, Nigeria.
2. Find out if the techniques used by teachers at the upper basic level differ on the basis of experience.
3. Find out if the techniques used by teachers at the upper basic level differ on the basis of qualification.

Research Questions

This study provided answers to the following questions:

1. What are the various techniques for the teaching of composition at the upper basic level in Ilorin, Nigeria?
2. Do teachers' techniques differ on the basis of their experience?
3. Do teachers' techniques differ on the basis of their qualification?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested:-

H01: There is no significant difference in the teachers' techniques based on experience.

H02: There is no significant difference in the teachers' techniques based on qualification.

Scope of the Study

This study involved an analysis of the techniques for teaching composition in English at the upper basic level in Ilorin, Nigeria. Specifically, upper basic levels in twenty randomly selected schools in Ilorin, Nigeria.

A researcher-designed questionnaire was used to elicit information from the subjects. Data collected was analyzed using frequency count and percentage to answer all research question, while all the hypotheses were tested using the ANOVA statistical technique.

The Status of English in Nigeria

The English language came to Nigeria as it did in other English speaking Africa countries as a result of colonization and exploration by the British settlers in the sixteen century. From that period to the present time, there had been changes in the face and fate of English language in Nigeria. When it first came, it was regarded as a language of imposition and was thereby seen as a foreign language.

The language occupies a significant place in the country's educational system. It is accorded an important status not only because it is a core subject in the school curriculum but also because it has the potential for promoting creative thinking and was adopted as a service language for other subjects in the Nigerian school curriculum. In recognition of the importance of English language in enhancing educational attainment as well as for improving communication ability of citizens, the government had made it a core subject.

Thus, English language is more than just another subject on the school curriculum because it is significantly related to general academic performance. It is equally a language of instruction for the country to accentuate our technological development and to progress technologically in order to enhance overall national development. Nigerian learners' access to cultural and scientific knowledge of the world is largely through English

accentuate our technological development and to progress technologically in order to enhance overall national development. Nigerian learners' access to cultural and scientific knowledge of the world is largely through English language.

There are five domains of the function of English in Nigeria. These are official, education, mass-media, religious observance and interpersonal relations. The linkage between the national and international role of English in Nigeria is best summed by Adegbite (2003) who stated that English performs three broad functions of 'accommodation, participation and social mobility'.

English language as an educational instrument has the power both to create and transform social realities, especially when man's intellectual, moral, social, economic and political developments largely depend on the instrumentality of language. Noting that in the educational domain, English performs a dual role. First it is a language of instruction, as well as a course of study in Nigeria and many other countries of the world.

The Place of Composition in the Upper Basic School Curriculum

The word 'curriculum' came from the Latin word, 'curare', meaning to 'run a course', 'a course' or an event to purposefully go through within a specific period of time. Curriculum is seen as an intention, plan or prescription and ideas about what one would like to happen in schools. Curriculum can also be viewed as the total experiences which all learners must be exposed to, that is the content, performance objectives, learners and teachers activities, learning material and evaluation.

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The basic education according to Torres (2000), is that type of

Education capable of meeting the basic learning needs of children, youth and adults. Basic education therefore, is the starting point in education which involves learning how to learn and move on to continuing education, life-long education and mass literacy.

The Upper Basic School is the stage in the UBE programme following the primary education and finally the Senior Secondary School. It is a nine year programme and a final stage of compulsory education. The UBE scheme curriculum spells out five broad objectives to be achieved at the end of its implementation. These, according to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2002) include:

- a. Providing free compulsory basic education for every Nigerian child of school age.
- b. Developing in the entire citizenry a strong consciousness for education and a strong commitment to its vigorous promotion.
- c. Reducing drastically the incidence of drop-outs from the formal school system through relevant quality and efficiency.
- d. Catering for the learning needs of young persons who for one reason or the other had to interrupt their schooling through appropriate complementary approaches to the provision and promotion of basic education.
- e. Ensuring the acquisition of the appropriate levels of literacy, numeracy, manipulative communication and life skills as well as the ethical moral and civil value for laying a solid foundation for lifelong learning.

Strategies for Effective Teaching and Learning of Composition

Composition is usually a difficult skill to teach, assess or evaluate. Methods applicable to the teaching of the skills of listening, speaking and reading should be emphasized or combined to teach composition. Adding that, the communicative method can form the introductory lesson to written composition. Audio-lingual method can also be combined to correct their grammatical errors or pronunciation that could affect spelling.

Therefore, teaching strategies in the teaching and learning of composition in English language is hence the importance of this discussion. Composition is perhaps the highest skill to demonstrate competence and performance in any language. In language acquisition a child begins to speak by producing meaningless sounds to meaningful sounds. He graduates from a one-word stage to combining words; before he uses the language the way he likes. Similarly, in writing, a learner begins by writing the letters of the alphabet before using them to form words and eventually, chaining words to form different structures.

Teaching and learning writing is easier when we break apart these layers. This is why Harris, Karen, Graham & Steve (1992) suggest on their writing assessments on the five features of Effective Writing. By focusing on what is most important in a piece of written communication, these features not only provide teachers with a more objective set of criteria for assessing writing; they also agreed it provide students with a framework for reading and improving their own writing. These five features of Effective Writing are focus, organization, support and elaboration, style, and conventions.

Focus

Focus is the topic/subject established by the writer in response to the writing task. The presence, therefore, of a focus must be determined in light of the method of development chosen by the writer. If the reader is confused about

method of development chosen by the writer. If the reader is confused about the subject matter, the writer has not effectively established a focus. If the reader is engaged and not confused, the writer probably has been effective in establishing a focus.

Organization

Organization is the progression, relatedness, and completeness of ideas. The writer establishes for the reader a well-organized composition, which exhibits a constancy of purpose through the development of elements forming an effective beginning, middle, and end.

Support and Elaboration

Support and Elaboration is the extension and development of the topic/subject. The writer provides sufficient elaboration to present the ideas and/or events clearly. Two important concepts in determining whether details are supportive are the concepts of relatedness and sufficiency. Effective use of concrete, specific details strengthen the power of the response.

Style

Style is the control of language that is appropriate to the purpose, audience and context of the writing task. The writer's style is evident through word choice and sentence fluency. Skilful use of precise, purposeful vocabulary enhances the effectiveness of the composition

Conventions

Conventions involve correctness in sentence formation, usage, and mechanics. The writer has control of grammatical conventions that are appropriate to the writing task. Errors, if present, do not impede the reader's understanding of the ideas conveyed.

What is the task asking you to do?

compare - examine the characteristics to demonstrate their similarities and differences; contrast - examine the characteristics of the objects to demonstrate their differences; analyze - consider the various components and explain the relationships among them; discuss - present the different aspects of a question and problem;

evaluate - examine the various sides of a question to reach a normative judgment. Analyze the task

Analysing the question involves identifying three kinds of words that you would find in most essay questions:

- Directive or Instructive words: tell you what to do with the content words e.g. discuss, compare, contrast, evaluate or analyze.
- Content words: tell you what the question is about.
- Limiting words: limit the focus of the question
e.g. a particular time, period, theory, place or number

These words have been identified in the following example of an essay question:

Directive or Instructional words (bold)

Content words (underlined)

↓
Discuss the *similarities* between *two examples* according to the *gendered* nature of work.

↖ ↗
Limiting words (italics)

Source: Parson G. (1985)

Outlining the Essay.

Outline

After analyzing the essay topic, the components should be organized to form an essay outline (or plan). The outline helps to ensure that your essay

has a coherent, logical structure. It also facilitates the preparation of your essay by guiding your reading, note-taking and writing. Outlines also enable you to assign relative weighting to the different components of your answer by differentiating which points are central, and which the peripheral. They will thus assist your research effort.

Outlines, however, are not set in concrete terms. The outline should be open to revision as research progresses, but always check that the new outline continues to address directly the essay topic.

Structure of the essay

The figure below provides you with a visual representation of the overall structure of an essay showing:

- a. The key aspects to be included in the introduction;
- b. The relationship between the introduction of the essay and each of the issues discussed in the body or middle of the paper; and
- c. The aspects contained in the conclusion.

Brainstorming

Essay topics should be considered in detail, jot down all useful ideas as it occurs on a piece of paper and maybe rough out a sort of skeleton answer. In the first place this may be easier to do starting with a circle in the middle of the page and extending lines out as ideas occur to you. Once you have lots of points jotted down, in the order they occurred to you, then you can move to the next stage which is where you tentatively put numbers by the points.

Polishing

Once the drafted and redrafted of the essay have been prepared, it must be polished so that a presentation of the best possible essay is ensured for best possible grade. Use the following checklist as a guide.

- a. Have I answered the question, including all parts of the question?
- b. Have I avoided the use of personal pronouns (first person)?
- c. Have I included a reference list or bibliography?
- d. Have I kept within the word length?
- e. Have I proofread my work to ensure correct spelling/grammar?
- f. Have I put the correct cover sheet information on the front of my essay?
- g. Have I referenced correctly?
- h. Is there a clear structure, including an introduction, logical body and conclusion?

Again, there has emerged a process-oriented approach to teaching writing. Recognizing that writing is a complex, recursive, dynamic nonlinear process, experts in the field of composition have developed and tested instructional methods more in keeping with the true nature of the act of writing. Looked at this way, it becomes obvious that the process has a number of distinct stages (Parson 1985; Holdzkom, Reed, Porter and Rubin, 1982; Hillocks 1986; Wesdorp 1983; Applebee 1981). These include:

Prewriting

The writer gathers information and plays with ideas during the prewriting stage. Prewriting activities may include drawing, talking, thinking, reading, listening to tapes and records, discussion, role playing, interviews, problem-solving and decision making activities, conducting library research, and so on. Research shows that students who are encouraged to engage in an array of prewriting experiences evidence greater writing achievement than those enjoined to "get to work" on their writing without this kind of preparation (Holdzkom, et al., 1982; Wesdorp, 1983 and Parson, 1985).

Drafting

The writer develops his/her topic on paper (or a computer screen) during the drafting stage. Beginning may be painful and difficult, producing false starts and frustration in the writer. In the process-oriented approach, the focus is on content, not the mechanics of writing.

Revising

During this stage, the writer makes whatever changes he/she feels are necessary. Revision may involve additions and deletions; changes in syntax, sentence structure, and organization; and in some cases, starting over completely. According to Westdorp (1983) and other researchers, the revision stage is most productive of superior final products if it includes input from teachers or fellow students.

Editing

Polishing of the draft takes place in the editing stage. The writer gives attention to mechanics such as spelling, punctuation, grammar, and handwriting, and may also make minor lexical and syntactic changes.

Publication

Publication refers to the delivery of the writing to its intended audience. Sommers and Collins (1984), Smith (1982), Westdorp (1983) have found that student motivation and achievement are enhanced when a student's work is "published" for a larger audience than the teacher.

Holdzkom, et al. (1982), Keech and Thomas (1979), other researchers and reviewers have identified the provision of a language-rich environment as a producer of positive outcomes in writing achievement. In addition to the prewriting activities cited above, researchers have found the following to be conducive to enhancing writing motivation and skill:

- * Using a letter box to increase student-teacher communication
- * Journals, free writing, stream-of-consciousness writing
- * Writing poetry, compiling lists, free association writing

- * Genre schemes and special formats, e.g., journalistic forms and conventions
- * Audio-visual stimulation, such as films, drama, photography, sculpture and dancing (Keech and Thomas, 1979).

In general, practice of any of the language arts has been found to enhance facility in the others. Reading and writing skills are closely related, and researchers have found that increased reading experiences also enhance writing skill development (Bruno, 1981).

Appraisal of Literature Review

We can be fairly certain that the sub processes of composing interrupt each other. The writer moves from high-level plans to the transcription of words and back to higher-level planning, re-reading what has been written, reconstructing plans already made, making new plans, generating new data, or performing editing of some kind. This bobbing up-and-down among various levels has been examined most systematically.

The study by Kapka and Oberman (2001) showed that modeling to students to write in different genres and different writing knowledge and abilities was effective to develop students' writing abilities. In their Study, Kowalewski, Murphy and Starns, (2002) found out that when a teacher gave enough time to students to write, he/she became a model for the writing process, he/she used the well-written samples in the writing process and he/she made writing the aim, students' writing abilities developed.

The poor level of achievement in many subject areas may be due to poor foundation in English language writing at the primary school level. There are also several researchers' reports which support that language inefficiency invariably leads to poor writing performance (Kapka and Oberman, 2001; Kowalesi et al., 2002).

Instrumentation and Data Collection

The instrument for this study was a researcher-designed questionnaire, titled "Teacher Variables Questionnaire" (TVQ), which was used to elicit information from the respondents. The questionnaire was grouped into two sections, A and B. Section A sought demographic characteristics which is designed to get information about a teacher's gender, qualification and experience.

Section B of the instrument focused on identifying the techniques used in teaching writing composition in relation to the human and material requirements of the respondents. Item scale of measurement is the four point scale was used i.e. Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The questionnaire consist of twenty (20) items in form of direct questions on which the respondents are required to provide answer on four point likert type scale.

On ensuring the validity of the instrument, the instrument was submitted to specialists in research as well as tests and measurement for their input and appropriate advice and guidance.

Procedure for Data Collection

The information for this study was based on primary data collected through the use of questionnaire. The teachers were made to realize the importance of the study to the teaching of writing composition in their various schools. The researcher explained certain key words in the questionnaire to the teachers in the schools visited as their cooperation were required in order to ensure appropriate feedback.

Data Analysis Techniques

In this study, data collected were analyzed using mean frequency counts and percentage to answer the research questions. The ANOVA

Statistical technique was also employed to test all the research hypotheses.

Result:

Demographic characteristics of the respondents

This section describes personal information of the respondents' teachers using frequency counts and percentage. The output is shown below:

Table 1: Gender Distribution of the Teachers

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	279	46.5
Female	321	53.5
Total	600	100

Table 1 showed that out of 600 sampled teachers 279 (46.5 %) were males while the rest 321 (53.3 %) were females.

Table 2: Qualification Distribution of the Teachers

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
NCE	262	43.6
B.Ed	300	50.0
M.Ed	38	6.30
Total	600	100

Table 2 showed that out of 600 sampled teachers 262 (43.6 %) are holders of NCE, 300 (50 %) are holders of B.Ed, while the M.Ed certificate

holders are 38 (6.3 %).

Table 3: level of Experience (years) Distribution of the Teachers

Years of Experience	Frequency	Percentage
1 – 9	124	20.6
10- 19	273	45.5
20-35	203	33.8
Total	600	100

Table 3 showed that out of 600 sampled teachers 124 (43.6%) fell within 1 - 9 years, 273 (45.5 %) within 10 - 19 years and 203 (33.8 %) are within 20 - 35 years.

HYPOYHESIS TESTING

Two research hypotheses were postulated in this study. The hypotheses were tested using ANOVA statistical technique at level of significance 0.05.

HO₁: there is no significant difference in the teacher's techniques based on the qualification

Table 4: ANOVA Analysis showing Difference in Teachers Techniques Based on Qualification

Sources of Variance	SS	DF	MS	Calculated f. value	Critical f - value	Ranks
Between Groups	130.034	2	65.017			
Within Groups	1162.716	597	11.987	5.424	3.00	Reject
Total	1292.750	599				

Critical level of significance = 0.05

This implies that there is a significant difference in teachers techniques based on qualifications.

H02: There is no significant difference in the teacher's techniques based on experience.

Table 5: ANOVA Analysis showing Difference in Teacher's Technique Based on Experince.

Sources of Variance	SS	DF	MS	Calculated f. value	Critical f - value	Ranks
Between Groups	121.042	2	58.211			
Within Groups	1032.516	596	10.882	5.323	3.00	Reject
Total	1181.840	599				

Critical level of significance = 0.05

This implies that there is a significant difference in teachers' techniques based on experience.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The secondary schools in Nigeria are far behind time in offering multiple pathways to the teaching and learning composition writing. Little wonder that the system has been witnessing steady decline with the percentage of students who failed English language examinations fluctuating between 55 % and 75 % in the past ten years. The effect of this is that secondary school students who find their way into the university are already at a disadvantage due to poor background and preparation in writing.

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Schools and, especially in the upper basic level in Nigeria, should be provided with adequate and a variety of instructional media. If teachers in the upper basic level in Nigeria are to assume new roles and use new technology and supported instructional tools, they should become familiar with a variety of instructional delivery methods. Therefore, it is strongly recommended that the learning environment in Nigeria should generally be given priority attention by state and federal governments so that students can learn well.

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